

CREATION OF GEODESIC FRAMEWORKS FOR GEODYNAMIC MONITORING IN "KANDIM GAS FIELD" BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract. Today, it is no secret that the Republic of Uzbekistan is one of the leaders in the world in terms of gas fields and gas production. There are several gas fields in the regions of Kashkadarya, Bukhara and Fergana Valley, as well as in the Republic of Karakalpakstan. This article is dedicated to the creation of a geodetic basis and geodetic measurement works for geodynamic monitoring in the "Kandim gas field" of Bukhara region.

Аннотация. Не секрет, что сегодня Республика Узбекистан является мировым лидером по месторождениям и добыче газа. Есть несколько газовых месторождений в Кашкадарьинской, Бухарской областях, Ферганской долине и Республике Каракалпакстан. Статья посвящена созданию геодезической основы геодинамического мониторинга и геодезических измерений на Кандымском газовом месторождении в Бухарской области.

In his address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Sh. Mirziyoev, said: "In order to provide raw materials for a number of important sectors of the economy, including chemistry, oil and gas, energy, electrical engineering, construction materials, jewelry industry, first of all, it is necessary to fundamentally develop the field of geological exploration. .." he said.

Gas fields are formed under a certain temperature and pressure in the areas where organic remains of the Mesozoic period, i.e., the remains of plants and creatures, have accumulated. Exploration and development of oil and gas fields in Uzbekistan, which has a 120-year history, began in 1885. If we look at history, in

fact, when Alexander the Great marched to Central Asia in the 4th century BC, they met "karamoy" in this country, but they did not know how to use it.

In 1898, a group of Russian businessmen under the leadership of engineer S.A. Kovalevsky began to search for oil fields in the villages of Chimyan (Fergana Valley). They started drilling the 1st well in 1901, and in 1904 they managed to open an oil layer at a depth of 278 meters. This well began to produce 130 tons of oil per day. "Chimyon" oil company was established on the basis of this field. Also, in 1901, oil erupted from 168 meters in Moylisoy, yielding 25 tons of oil per day. In 1903, the enterprise was founded on this basis. An oil well was drilled in Yorkoton near Chimyon in 1907 and put into operation in 1910 [6].

We would like to briefly highlight the work of creating a geodetic basis for geodynamic monitoring on the example of the "Kandim gas field" located in the territory of Bukhara region.

"Kandim gas field" is located in the eastern part of Bukhara region, bordering the Republic of Turkmenistan, on the territory of Karakol and Olot districts, and is mainly located in the desert region. The topography of the area is dune sand, the height of the hills is from 4 to 8 m, and their height is from 178 to 191 m above sea level.

Hydrography The field is located in a waterless area. The nearest reservoir is located 10 km north of the Kandim mine. Hydrography There are small (mainly saline) lakes located south of the mines. Larger salt lakes Shurkak and Madonkul are located 1 km south of the mine. Tuz lake is located 8 km to the east of the field. The Karakum collector passes 9-12 km from the north and east.

The plants are considered to be very lifeless, and are in the form of grass that burns completely during the summer.

Settlements - the nearest settlement is the settlement of Karadzhi, 14 km east of the field. The city of Bukhara is 75 km to the north-east, and the regional center Karakol is 28 km to the east of Yesa Square. The road network is mainly

represented by dirt roads and main roads. An asphalt road (a branch from the main Samarkand - Bukhara - Chardzow road) approaches the deposit from the village of Karadzhi. The Bukhara-Karakol-Turkmanabat railway passes 25 km southeast of the mine.

Physical and geographical features - the climate is sharply continental, characterized by large seasonal and daily temperature changes. Summer is dry and hot, the temperature drops to 40-44° during the day and 10° at night. Winter is very cold and snowy, the temperature drops to -20-25°.

The duration of the field period is 8.5 months (from March 1 to November 15)

"LUKOIL Uzbekistan Operating Company" limited liability company dug dozens of gas wells in the region and started continuous gas production.

The area where the gas field is located is divided by geologists into several small shells. The main areas with gas reserves are also known. Based on this, the points and direction of geodynamic monitoring are determined.

It is known that geodynamic monitoring refers to the vertical and horizontal movement of the earth's plates, identified surface cracks [2]. In addition to the geological analysis of underground processes, the detection of changes in the earth's crust and plates is also determined through geodynamic monitoring.

A geodetic base will be created in the area designated for geodynamic monitoring. First, the types of geodetic points are determined depending on the relief of the area, the type of soil layers, the period and depth of freezing of the earth's surface, and the type of observation equipment.

Based on the state of connection to the geodetic base, previously performed geodetic works in this area are studied. After studying all the data, a technical project is drawn up [3]. In the technical project, the territory of the geodynamic polygon, the geodetic points that make up the geodetic base participating in it, the location of the geodetic points in the area where geodynamic measurements are

planned, the number and types of points, their height. and depth, documents to be formalized, etc. are needed

In the case of the "Kandim gas field" located in the territory of Bukhara region, when geodynamic monitoring is carried out, the creation of a geodetic base in the sequence of the following scheme (Fig. 1) increases efficiency

Picture 1. The scheme of creating a geodetic basis for conducting geodynamic monitoring

When conducting geodynamic monitoring, we can justify the creation of a geodetic base as follows:

1. In order to create a technical project, the territory is studied, the geodetic works performed previously are analyzed;
2. A technical project is drawn up;
3. Geodetic points are prepared based on the technical project;
4. Geodetic points will be established on site, relevant documents will be formalized;
5. After at least 6 months have passed since the installation of geodetic points in accordance with the instructions, geodetic measurement works will be carried out;
6. A technical report will be drawn up based on the results of the work performed.

When carrying out these monitoring works, based on the placement of geodetic points, the types of geodetic points are determined based on the accuracy of measurement and climatic factors.

Since geodetic surveying in the Kandim gas field is carried out with high accuracy and the depth of freezing of the ground is 50-100 cm, fundamental markers with a depth of more than 2 meters and 146 types of geodetic points with an installation depth of more than 150 cm recommended to use.

It is recommended that the point installation scheme consists of a network distributed in four directions every 90° from the center of the gas field. The average distance between points is 500-800 meters.

The demand for geodetic measurement works for conducting geodynamic monitoring will consist of the following:

II-class leveling works are carried out through the geodetic grid placed from the starting point and are carried out again to the starting point;

The horizontal location of the geodetic points relative to the starting point, that is, their coordinates, is determined. In this case, it is recommended to determine the coordinates using high-precision GPS devices. Availability of data

from at least 4 satellites during the period of operation of GPS devices, recording interval

It is required to be 10 seconds, to be $PDOP \leq 3$, and not to block the antenna 150 above the horizon where the antenna is placed.

Creating a geodetic base for conducting geodynamic monitoring is very important in performing high-precision geodetic work. The geodetic works performed with the created geodetic base are divided into stages, and as a result of comparing the results of the geodetic measurement work performed in the next stages with the previous works, the changes occurring on the surface of the earth and their dimensions are determined. As a result of these works, it will be possible to monitor geodynamic changes.

Summary

Currently, most of the production state organizations and organizations, including "Republika Aerogeodeziya Enterprise", "UzGASHKLITI" DUK, are working on creating a geodetic base for geodynamic monitoring. Creating a geodetic base for geodynamic monitoring in oil and gas fields The state of subsidence or changes in the earth's surface that may occur as a result of the mining of its products is determined.

it will be possible to monitor the removals.

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